

Research and Bioinformatics Librarian Rachael Pereira (she/her)

"I enjoy collaborating with clinical research teams, providing informational sessions on library and bioinformatics resources, and solving problems."

Bio

While studying biology as an undergrad, Rachael became fascinated by genomics and information science. She earned a Master's degree in Library and Information Science and landed a role as a research librarian in an academic medical library. Within three years she became a critical member of her library's team as a research impact and bioinformatics librarian. Rachael works directly with faculty to manage and track their publications, update NIH biosketches, create research dissemination strategies, and assess research impact via a wide variety of routine and alternative metrics. Rachael is skilled at using bibliometrics to report research impact for program review, grants, and tenure and promotion packets. Rachael also uses bioinformatics tools in her data consultations. Rachael shares her knowledge through LibGuides and classes. As she hones new skills in research impact and computational informatics, she presents her innovations in presentations at medical library conferences and in workshops for her campus.

Education: BS, Biology; Master's, Library and Information Science
Years of experience: 3
Work location: Library, classrooms, remote work

Goals

- Improved skills in visualization and data management software programs
- Develop new educational offerings for patrons
- Identify time efficiencies wherever possible in her job

Software attitude & use

- Open to learning new tools
- Rachael is learning D3JS and wants to improve her skills in R
- General: Microsoft Office Suite and Google Workspace
- Collaboration: Box, Trello, Slack, Zoom
- Specialized resources include bibliographic resources (e.g., PubMed, Scopus), EndNote, evaluation tools (e.g., ORCID, Metrics Toolkit, InCites, the institutional repository). Research resources (e.g., Ensembl, NCBI, OpenRefine, Python, R, R Studio, Tableau, VOSViewer, and Jupyter Notebooks)

Outputs

- Conference presentations & posters
- Class materials, LibGuides, library website content
- Co-authorship on systematic reviews from her research librarian days
- Visualizations for grants

Pain Points

- Analyzing and compiling information for research impact is very time consuming
- Lack of interoperability/formatting issues when transferring information from one system to another

Motivators

- Collaborate effectively with clinical teams, leading to synergy, recognition, and (sometimes) co-authorship
- Outreach to inform the research community that the library supports bioinformatics tools, tracking and reporting research impact, and data management
- Increase outreach to research and clinical teams
- Meet researchers' needs to help them showcase their publication record and impact

Wants/Needs

- The ability to quickly learn and leverage new technologies to meet increased demand for electronic data in a wide variety of formats
- Time to attend continuing education classes, to practice and build skills, and to develop library-based classes
- Reduce last-minute requests for biosketch updates or help with NIH Public Access Policy compliance (depositing articles to PubMed Central) through effective marketing

Professional Development

Department supports travel to conferences and workshops, and purchasing informational resources

The academic health center of which Rachael's library is a part supports a percentage of the librarians' college tuition in the associated university

Rachael benefited from direct mentorship by research impact librarians at her library, and she now mentors a junior colleague